

APPROACHES OF COMBINED WEED CONTROL SYSTEM IN MATURE TEA PLANTATIONS

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Abstract

An experiment was conducted at the Bangladesh Tea Research Institute Farm & Bilashcherra Experimental Farm during 2019–2020 to determine the best weed management combinations for managing weeds in matured tea plantations. Five treatments were used in the experiment, each of which was duplicated three times using RCBD. Every two weeks, data on the percentage of weed reduction and the weekly harvesting of green leaves were gathered. Every treatment exhibited a somewhat notable fluctuation in the yield of made tea and the percentage of weed growth compared to the control. The treatment (T₃), Chilling + Indaziflam (pre-emergent herbicide) + Paraquat (post-emergent herbicide) showed maximum reduction of weed density (67%) over the control followed by (T₅) simultaneous application of Indaziflam + Paraquat + Sickling, where the weed reduction percentage is 63.46%. Therefore, higher mean yield (1837 kg/ha) was obtained from T₃ which is following by T₅, Where the mean yield is 1785 kg/ha over the control. Among the treatments used, Chilling + Indaziflam + Paraquat produced the best gross margin return and was also shown to be the most cost-effective. It is advised that the most cost-effective and efficient combinations for managing weeds in established tea farms are Chilling + Indaziflam + Paraquat, taking into account all the parameters.

Keywords: Mature Tea, Weeds, Integration, Reduction, Yield, Cost-effective.

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Introduction

Globally, tea is considered as the second largest & cheapest popular beverage after water. Its area of cultivation & production percentages is significantly increasing day by day not only in Bangladesh but also in the whole world, where weed act as one of the major limiting factor on its expansion. They only become troublesome when the farm is expected to suffer substantial economic losses. These troublesome weeds cause significant financial losses in developing as well as industrialized countries despite advancements in technology. (Auld, 2004). Weeds are commonly strong plants and that's why their demands for mineral nutrients are usually excessive. In tea, the weeds can consume up to 252 kg of soil nutrients per hectare per year. (Chakravartee and Barbora, 1995). In addition to competing with the tea plants for basic needs, they also provide a habitat for a variety of diseases and pests. For sustainable productivity, tea plants require optimum agronomic maintenance like other plantation crops. However, weeds are the ones who absorb and release huge quantities of water, and this loss is amplified during dry spells. Weeds hinder tea because they compete with it for nutrients, moisture, light, and space. Thus, it leads to the reduction of plant growth and yield of tea.

Uncontrolled weed growth in tea plantations can result in a 10–50% reduction in yield. (Rajkhowa et. al., 2005; Deka & Barua, 2015). Because of weed infestation the global tea industry's yearly crop loss has been assessed to be 146 million kg. It is about to 14-15% crop loss of the total crop production (Rana et. al., 2020). Globally, weeds damage crops to an even greater extent than other pests.

Normally in mature tea plantations, factors like large ground exposure, heavy rainfall, use of nitrogenous fertilizer trigger the profuse weed growth. Ground exposure during land clearing & after pruning phases initiates enormous growth of weed in tea plantations. Under the humid conditions, the weed grows rapidly during the period of rainfall, when tea is heavily flushed. The majority of tea garden laborers frequently engage on plucking and other essential intercultural activities during this period, that's why it is quite difficult to control weed by manually. Normally in the tea gardens of Bangladesh, Weeding has been executed chemically (with herbicides) or manually (sickling, cheeling, and hoeing). However, maintaining weed-free conditions in these areas with hand tools or a single herbicide application isn't always feasible. Man days and a certain amount of round spray are needed regularly. Additionally, the price of weeding accounts for roughly 10% to 14% of all the overall cost of field operations. Additionally, it accounts for 4-5% of the entire cost of producing made tea, coming in second only to fertilizer application and plucking. (Prematilake, 2003). The rising cost of herbicides and the high cost of labor make weeding more and more expensive every day. For sustainable production of tea, methods for effectively and inexpensively controlling weeds in established plantations are crucial.

On the other hand, weeds may become habituated to and tolerant of such methods if only a few or one methods is applied to manage them over an extended period of time. (Bhowmic, 1997). The use of alternative weed management techniques, such integrated weed management (IWM), is becoming more and more popular these days. (Pannell, 1990; Swanton and Weise 1991; Clements, Weise and Swanton, 1994; Auld, 2004). Integrated Weed Management (IWM) employs a variety of different long-term weed management tactics, including mechanical removal, biological agents, genetic characteristics, cultural approaches, and chemical weed control. For the remaining approaches to remain suitable for usage in the future whenever the reliance on one technique is reduced. (Swanton and Weise, 1991). Therefore, a variety of management techniques are employed in IWM to prevent weeds from developing the ability to adjust to a continually shifting environment. The experiment was conducted to determine the most effective and sustainable combination of weed management strategies for managing weeds in matured tea plantations.

Materials and Methods

The experiment was carried out at Bangladesh Tea Research Institute & Bilascherra Experimental Farm during 2019-20 in mature tea plot with varied stand weeds. The experiment was carried out with five treatments and three replications using randomized complete block design. The plot size was 4.0×4.0 m². T₁= Control, T₂= Chilling (Mechanical control) + Pendimethalin (pre-emergent herbicide) + Paraquat (post-emergent herbicide), T₃= Chilling (Mechanical control) + Indaziflam (pre-emergent herbicide) + Paraquat (post-emergent herbicide), T₄= Simultaneous application of Pendimethalin + Paraquat + Sickling, T₅= Simultaneous application of Indaziflam + Paraquat + Sickling. Using a knapsack sprayer, herbicide treatments were given after the weeds had completely covered the ground and before they began to flower. Visual rating on a 100-point scale (0 being no control and 100 representing complete control) was used to evaluate the efficacy. . The mean data were expressed in percentages. Yield data was collected in terms of weekly weight of green leaves. Using the Statistix-10 application, all gathered data have been collated and statistically examined.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 demonstrates that T₃ outperforms the control in terms of weed reduction percentage (67%) and is followed by T₅ (63.46%). T₂ and T₄, which had weed reduction percentages for the trial period of 34.23% and 29.60% over the control, come after T₅. It can be noted that using Indaziflam and then Paraquat (T₃) after the chilling operation gives the highest

percentage of weed reduction and the longest period of weed-free state. It may be very useful in areas that have been pruned to LP and DSK. Simultaneous application of Indaziflam, Paraquat and after then sickling (T₅) give the second most weed reduction percentage which may be applied in other skiffed areas of tea plantation.

Similar outcomes were attained by [Kappro and Hall \(2011\)](#) using Indaziflam in forestry and turf. According to [Sharma's \(1980\)](#) research, pre-emergence efficacy of herbicides climbed linearly with dosage and provided effective control for a full 12-week period. [Perry with his scientists \(2011\)](#) showed that one application of Indaziflam may be able to manage certain summer and winter weeds. for 29 weeks after treatment. [Sebastian et al. \(2017\)](#) also reported on the long-term control of certain invasive annual grasses and the elimination of these invasive grasses' soil seed bank with the application of Indaziflam.

The results of various treatment combinations indicate that T₃ produced the highest mean yield (1837 kg/ha), followed by T₅, whose mean yield is 1785 kg/ha (Table 2). The yield from treatments T₄ (1716 kg/ha) and T₂ (1691 kg/ha) came after the yield from treatment T₅. T₁, where frequent practice was conducted, produced the lowest yield (1605 kg/ha). This result showed that T₃ had the highest yield, which was 14.45% higher than the control.

Table 1. Weed growth as percentage over various treatment combinations

Treatments	Weed growth%	Reduction of weed growth% over the control
Control	54.16 c	00
Chilling (Mechanical control) + Pendimithalin (pre-emergent herbicide) + Paraquat (post-emergent herbicide)	35.62 b	34.23%
Chilling (Mechanical control) + Indaziflam (pre-emergent herbicide) + Paraquat (post-emergent herbicide)	18.00 a	67%
Simultaneous application of Pendimithalin + Paraquat + Sickling	38.125 b	29.60%
Simultaneous application of Indaziflam + Paraquat + Sickling.	19.79 a	63.46%

According to DMRT, values inside columns denoted by distinct letter(s) differ significantly ($p \leq 0.05$).

Table 2. Yield gained from different treatment combination.

Treatments	Mean yield of green leaf (kg/ plot)	Mean yield of green leaf (kg/ ha)	Mean yield of made tea (kg/ ha)
T ₁	11.16 c	6,980 c	1,605 c
T ₂	11.76 b	7,350 b	1,691 b
T ₃	12.78 a	7,988 a	1,837 a
T ₄	11.94 b	7,463 b	1,716 b
T ₅	12.42 a	7,763 a	1,785 a
LSD at 5% level	0.56		
CV	1.75		

According to DMRT, values inside columns denoted by distinct letter(s) differ significantly ($p \leq 0.05$).

Table 3. Partial budget analysis of integrated weed management practices on the yield of tea.

Treatment	Yield of made tea (kg/ha)	Variable cost (Tk/ha)			Gross return (Tk/ha)	Gross margin (Tk/ha)
		Herbicide	Labour	Total		
T ₁	1605	2940	2040	4980	321000	316020
T ₂	1691	2980	12,155	15,135	338200	323065
T ₃	1837	3230	12,155	15,385	367400	352015
T ₄	1716	2980	5270	8250	343200	334950
T ₅	1785	3230	5270	8500	357000	348500

Supposing, price of Indaziflame group herbicide= 15000 Tk/litre, Pendimithaline= 1000 Tk/litre, Paraquat= 350 tk/litre, price of made tea =200 Tk/kg, Labour wage= 170 Tk/day.

Fig. 1. Correlation between weed growth% and mean yield kg/ plot.

Weed growth percentage and mean yield kg/plot parameter have a very strong negative relationship, as shown in Fig. 1. The yield parameter moves upward in response to a decrease in the percentage of weed growth and downward in response to an increase in the percentage of weed growth.

Conclusion

Considering yield of made tea and economic analysis viewpoint it can be concluded that, the application of Indaziflam and Paraquat following a chilling operation provides the highest percentage of weed reduction and the longest duration of weed-free conditions. To achieve better results, more research may be done combining novel herbicide molecules with other IWM components. Tea industry will be benefited by enhancement of crop yield by sustainable management of tea weeds for longer period of time in a cropping season.

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